

Procedure for Integration of an Articulated Robot Model in a Game Engine Environment

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The versatility and power of modern game engine platforms provide the potential for their use in creating real-time simulation environments within the robotics domain, particularly suitable for immersive and interactive experiences. Equipped with the comprehensive toolsets, extensive toolkits, and built-in features, these integrated development environments support the creation of real-time robot simulation models. Recently, Extended-Reality technology has been used in the development of human-machine interfaces in industrial robotics, in applications such as robot programming, system engineering, and personnel training. In this paper, the procedure for the integration of a vertically articulated robot's model in the Unity game engine is presented. The main goal of the procedure is to generate a 3D GameObject robot in Unity, starting from a 3D model of the robot obtained using 3D design software. Positioning of robot joints' local frames in a CAD environment for integration of a robot with Unity is described. The Articulation Body class from Unity's built-in physics engine, Nvidia PhysX, is used to integrate robot dynamics. Specific XML formats following open-source standards, equipped with elements and attributes specific to robot kinematic and dynamic structure and suitable add-ons, have been used. The procedure is verified using the 6DoF vertically articulated robots RL15 and AD100.

Key Words: Robot, Unity, Unreal Engine, Extended Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

Growing customer demands and global competition have driven the increasing need for integrating industrial robots with Industry 4.0 solutions. Articulated robot, sometimes also called a jointed, elbow, or anthropomorphic manipulator, Figure 1, is widely used in industry, medicine, research, and other domains [1]. The traditional methods of programming industrial robots include online programming methods, including the online programming with the use of a teach pendant - currently the most widespread method, and offli-

ne programming methods using industrial robot languages [2]. The programming of articulated robots with multiple degrees of freedom (DoFs) with traditional methods can present a challenging and time-consuming task, often requiring expert knowledge [2-3]. The ease of robot programming is one of the major factors to be considered when evaluating the efficiency and practical adoption of robots in industry. With the demands of personalized production, which primarily relate to higher product variation and drastically reduced batch sizes, the need for more intuitive and time-efficient robot programming methods has arisen [2-4].

Robot virtual simulators are widely used in the design and verification of robot trajectories, as well as in system engineering domains. Dedicated robot simulation software includes frameworks and libraries

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used as dynamics engines [5-6], and standalone simulators [7-8]. Over the years, the expansion of game engines and their capabilities has led to their increasing utilization in research involving robotics and multi-body system simulation. The versatility and power of modern game engine platforms such as Unity [9] and Unreal Engine [10] have opened up new possibilities for creating real-time simulation environments with immersive and interactive experiences within the robotics domain. Recently, Extended-Reality (XR) technology has been used in the development of human-machine interfaces for articulated industrial and educational desktop robots [2, 4, 11-13], in applications such as robot programming, system engineering, and personnel training [4].

Figure 1 - Articulated robots developed in the Lola Institute: RL15, AD100.

Although game engines are increasingly applied in robotics and multibody system simulations, most resources remain practice-oriented, with few peer-reviewed studies to offer systematic integration methodologies, due to the open-source nature of plugins and the multidisciplinary complexity of implementations [13].

In this paper, a practical workflow for integrating articulated robot models into the Unity game engine is presented. It combines two different XML file formats necessary to preserve both kinematic and dynamic properties, as well as visual features, with the complementary simulation environment used for assembly-defined links to ensure the correct transfer of robot segments' dynamic properties from the CAD model into Unity. Custom scripts are also developed to map controllers with robot joints, enabling visualization and robot motion simulation in the AR environment. The resulting models enable realistic dynamic model-based motion simulation of the robot within the Unity environment, include necessary robot visuals, and allow for motion controller setup. The integration enables realistic visualization, including augmented reality content and immersive interaction, enabling the design of advanced XR-enhanced robot programming interfaces using the Unity environment.

Kinematic model-based robot simulations in game engines such as Unity as well as in other virtual simulation environments generate robot motion through joint trajectories (path, velocity and acceleration) without considering forces, and dynamical properties such as masses, or inertia, which limits their use to path planning/feasibility. By contrast, dynamic model-based simulations, integrate mass and inertia parameters into a built-in physics engine allowing the engine to compute more realistic motion under gravity and loads. Additionally, Unity's built-in physics engine enables calculation of joint torques that can be used within robot design when selecting actuators [13]. Also, dynamics enable physically consistent collision handling in the sense that kinematic models detect only geometric overlaps, while dynamic models simulate contact forces, rebounds, and constraints. Such collision modeling is essential in object manipulation, workspace interaction, collaborative robotics, etc.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, a proposed procedure for the integration of a 3D robot model in Unity is presented. Section 3 presents the obtained results, demonstrating the integration of two articulated robots, RL15 and AD100, within the game engine IDE (integrated development environment). Section 4 provides concluding remarks.

2. METHODOLOGY

The main goal of the procedure is to generate a 3D GameObject robot in Unity, starting from a 3D model of the robot obtained using 3D design software. A physics engine is a software component or framework that simulates physical systems within a virtual environment by employing mathematical models to reproduce realistic interactions between physical bodies in the virtual environment in a manner akin to those in the real world [14]. Unity's built-in physics engine is based on the Nvidia PhysX engine, which provides for rigid-body dynamics and collision detection for real-time simulations. Its Articulation Body class [15] is used in this study for a robot's dynamic model integration, i.e., configuration of a robot as an open kinematic chain consisting of rigid bodies and joints. Articulation Body class from Nvidia PhysX enables building of physics articulations using Featherstone solver, such as robotic arms with GameObjects that are hierarchically organized [15].

In the procedure proposed herein, the import of robot model from 3D design software is performed by using open-source standards equipped with elements and attributes specific to robot kinematic and dynamic structure in the form of two XML file formats: URDF (Universal Robot Description Format) [16] and glTF (GL Transmission Format) [17]. SolidWorks [18] is used to design a 3D robot model as it allows model

exportation to the two mentioned XML formats using free and open-source add-ons. In Figure 2, the 3D model of robot RL15 designed in SolidWorks is presented.

Figure 2 - 3D model of robot RL15 designed in SolidWorks

URDF is an XML-based standard for representing robot models, such as kinematics, visual representations, and physical properties. While its hierarchical structure is conceptually similar to JSON, it is formally defined using XML schema. It provides several benefits, such as standardization, i.e. a unified way to represent robots, which facilitates integration with tools of software such as ROS [19] and enables interoperability, making it easier to transition between different robotics platforms, simulators, and visualizers. In addition to basic properties like kinematics and visual representation, a URDF file contains dynamic parameters such as the center of mass and inertia tensor. Figure 4a) illustrates a fragment of a URDF file.

If robot links are defined as single parts in SolidWorks CAD, the integration process of a 3D robot model in Unity starts with the procedure of exporting a URDF file from SolidWorks using the URDF exporter add-on [20]. Otherwise, if the robot links are defined as assemblies in the CAD model, the complementary simulation environment MATLAB Simscape [21] is used herein as an intermediate step to convert the robot model into URDF format. i.e., the URDF file is generated using MATLAB Simscape. In a previous study [13], it was established that using a URDF file obtained using Simulink for robot links defined as assemblies in CAD yields accurate joint torque calculations, due to the lack of development of the URDF exporter add-on. Figure 3 illustrates the decision flow to select the correct URDF exporting procedure for robot model integration into Unity.

Figure 3 - Decision flow for URDF exporter selection

```

a)
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<robot
  name="LOLA15_SWcadSLDASM">
  <link
    name="Lola15_Link_00">
    <inertial>
    <origin
      xyz="1.26208803834004E-06 0.127361187293972
      -0.000986343357538435"
      rpy="0 0 0" />
    <mass
      value="253.457969238907" />
    <inertia
      Ixx="4.901846976589"
      Iyy="6.53773929607727E-07"
      Izz="2.50894178271522E-05"
      Ixy="8.21691732760678"
      Iyz="-0.00827886945563918"
      Ixz="4.88124052950679" />
    </inertial>
    <visual>
    <origin
      xyz="0 0 0"
      rpy="0 0 0" />
    <geometry>
    <mesh
      filename=
      "package://LOLA15_SWcadSLDASM/meshes/Lola15_Link_00.STL"
    />
  </link>
  </robot>

b)
{
  "asset": {
    "generator": "SOLIDWORKSGLTF",
    "version": "2.0"
  },
  "extensionsUsed": [ "KHR_lights_punctual",
    "Solidworks_custom_properties" ],
  "scenes": 0,
  "scenes": [
    {
      "name": "Default - Display State-1",
      "nodes": [
        0
      ]
    }
  ],
  "nodes": [
    {
      "children": [
        1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
      ],
      "name": "LOLA15_SWcad"
    }
  ],
  "matrix": [
    [
      1, 0, 0, 0,
      0, 1, 0, 0,
      0, 0, 1, 0,
      0, 0, 0, 1
    ]
  ]
}

```

Figure 4 - a) Example of URDF file, b) Example of glTF file.

One notable drawback of URDF is that it doesn't contain textures, i.e., colors, which can be valuable for visualizing singularities in robotic kinematics models. For this reason, in this research, exporting a glTF file from SolidWorks using the glTF exporter add-on [22], was also used. The glTF file format was developed to address the need for transferring CAD scenes between different development environments, with a primary focus on visualization. As such, glTF is limited in that it does not support the definition of parameters that describe the dynamic properties of objects within the scene. Figure 4b) shows a fragment of a glTF file. In this research, the glTF file format is used to compensate for the URDF limitations regarding textures by replacing its textures.

For a proper URDF/glTF export, the rotational axes (z-axis) of the robot joints (and associated local frames) must be explicitly defined in SolidWorks. In Figure 5, the definition of local frames of robot links in SolidWorks is presented.

Figure 5 - Defining local frames of robot links in SolidWorks – 4th link.

With the URDF and glTF files prepared, the next step is their import into Unity, which is facilitated using URDF and glTF importer plugins [23-24]. Texture replacement is achieved by redefining the file path to the corresponding texture. The imported glTF robot model is removed afterwards. As a result, a fully integrated 3D model of the robot is obtained in Unity, featuring both dynamic properties and accurate color representation. In Figure 6, the RL15 robot in Unity using a URDF file before and after replacing the URDF textures with glTF file textures is presented.

Figure 6 - RL15 robot model with and without textures in Unity.

3. RESULTS

The developed procedure for integrating articulated robot models into Unity was successfully implemented. The RL15 and AD100 robots were imported using URDF and glTF files, enabling accurate visualization and dynamic behavior representation.

The proposed integration approach enables a comprehensive simulation of robot motion in Unity, both in terms of the dynamic model integration and visual representation. The presented procedure for robot model integration in Unity enables the following:

- utilizing Unity simulations within the design of the robot's mechanical structure, including actuator selection,
- collision simulation within the Unity environment,
- gripper-object interaction simulation,
- texture rendering combined with dynamic model-based simulation.

Potential applications include pick-and-place tasks, i.e. object manipulation, and collaborative robots (cobots).

One of the advantages of the ROS-Unity suite, besides the trajectory planner and control integration provided by ROS, is the ability to embed the robot's dynamic model within the Unity simulation

environment. On the other hand, for a standalone solution that avoids ROS and similar development environments to enable improved system performance on limited hardware, such as Android smartphones, and simplifying implementation [4], the robot model integration approach presented herein has proven effective.

The frame rate (FPS) is influenced by factors like script optimization, graphics settings, and 3D model complexity, and to improve performance, the robot's joints and links are simplified, without changing the dynamics parameters. Although FPS exceeds 300 on a PC, it is limited to 60 FPS on Meta Quest 3, which is sufficient for most robotic applications.

Figures 7 and 8 show the AR and VR visualization of the RL15 and AD100 robots within the Android-based developed application.

Figure 7 - Photo capture of scaled augmented robot RL15 in the designed robot programming Android app.

Figure 8 - User programming of the AD100 robot in AR/VR, with the Unity interface displayed on the monitor.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a detailed procedure for integrating a vertically articulated robot model into Unity was presented. The main goal was to generate a 3D

GameObject robot in Unity, starting from a 3D model created in SolidWorks CAD software. The integration was achieved using the Articulation Body class from the Nvidia PhysX engine, ensuring a realistic kinematic and dynamic simulation. Open-source XML formats and dedicated add-ons were used for the integration of the robot model from SolidWorks into Unity. URDF format was utilized to define the robot's kinematic and dynamic structure, while glTF format facilitated texture mapping and visualization. The presented procedure for integration of the robot model in Unity is a critical step that enables further development of the Unity-based real-time standalone robot simulation and programming environment, and advances XR-based human-robot interfaces.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Craig, J. J. Introduction to robotics: mechanics and control, 3 ed, *Pearson Education India*, 2009.
- [2] Ong S. K, Yew A.W .W, Thanigaivel N. K, Nee A. Y. C. Augmented Reality-Assisted Robot Programming System for Industrial Applications, *Robot. Comput.-Integr. Manuf.*, 61:101820, 2020.
- [3] Fang H. C, Ong S. K, Nee A. Y. C. Interactive Robot Trajectory Planning and Simulation Using Augmented Reality. *Robot. Comput.-Integr. Manuf.* 28, 227–237, 2012.
- [4] Devic A, Vidakovic J, Zivkovic N. Development of Standalone Extended-Reality-Supported Interactive Industrial Robot Programming System, *Machines*, 12(7):480, 2024.
- [5] Todorov E, Erez T, Tassa Y, MuJoCo: A Physics Engine for Model-Based Control, *In Proceedings of the 2012 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, Vilamoura-Algarve, Portugal. pp. 5026-5033, 2012.
- [6] DART: Dynamic Animation and Robotics Toolkit [internet]. [cited 16.12.2024] Available online: <https://dartsim.github.io/>.
- [7] Gazebo [internet]. [cited 1.1.2025]. Available online: <https://gazebo.org/home>.
- [8] Robot Simulator CoppeliaSim: Create, Compose, Simulate, Any Robot-Coppelia Robotics. [internet]. [cited 1.1.2025]. Available online: <https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/>.
- [9] Unity Real-Time Development Platform|3D, 2D, VR & AR Engine. [internet]. [cited 1.10.2024]. Available online: <https://unity.com>
- [10] Unreal Engine The Most Powerful Real-Time 3D Creation Tool. [internet]. [cited 1.12.2024.] Available online: <https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/>
- [11] Lotsaris K, Gkournelos C, Fousekis N, Kousi N, Makris S. AR Based Robot Programming Using Teaching by Demonstration Techniques, *Procedia CIRP*, 97:459-463, 2021.
- [12] Kapinus M, Materna Z, Bambušek D, Beran V, Smrž, P. Arcor2: Framework for collaborative end-user management of industrial robotic workplaces using augmented reality, *arXiv:2306.08464*, 2023.
- [13] Dević A. D, Vidaković J. Z, Slavković N. P, Lazarević M. P. & Živković N. Lj. A system engineering approach for robot manipulator design using game engine simulation and computational modeling. *Paper presented at the 10th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Mechanics, Niš, Serbia (SSM 2025)*, June 2025.
- [14] Bennett J. H. How realistically can contemporary platoon-level infantry combat be simulated using First-Person Shooter (FPS) video games?, *Doctoral dissertation, King's College London*, 2017.
- [15] Articulations-NVIDIA PhysX SDK 3.3.4 Documentation. [internet]. [cited 1.12.2024.]. Available online: <https://docs.nvidia.com/-gameworks/content/-gameworkslibrary/physx/guide/3.3.4/Manual/Articulations.html?highlight=articulation>.
- [16] URDF-ROS documentation. [internet]. [cited 1.2.2025.]. Available online: <https://wiki.ros.org/-urdf/XML/robot>.
- [17] glTF-Runtime 3D Asset Delivery. [internet]. [1.2.2025.] Available online: <https://www.khronos.org/glTF/>
- [18] 3D CAD Design Software|SOLIDWORKS. [internet]. [cited 1.12.2024.]. Available online: <https://www.solidworks.com/media/solidworks-2020-improved-performance>.
- [19] ROS: Home. ROS2 v.humble. [internet]. [cited 1.2.2025.] Available online: <https://www.ros.org/>
- [20] Sw_urdf_exporter-ROS Wiki. [internet]. [cited 1.9.2025] Available online: https://wiki.ros.org/-sw_urdf_exporter
- [21] The MathWorks, Inc., Simscape Multibody Link User's Guide, Natick, MA, USA: MathWorks, [internet]. [1.9.2025]. Available online: <https://www.mathworks.com/products/simscape.html>
- [22] NEW Extended Reality (XR) Exporter from SOLIDWORKS CAD. [internet]. [cited 1.12.2025.]. Available online: <https://www.solidworks.com/me-dia/-newextended-reality-xr-exporter-solidworks-cad>

[23]URDF-Importer. [internet]. [cited 1.12.2025.]. Available online: <https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/URDF-Importer/tree/main>

[24]GLTF-Importer UnityGLTF. [internet]. [cited 1.12.-2025.] Available online: <https://github.com/KhronosGroup/UnityGLTF/releases/tag/release%2F2.17.0>

REZIME

POSTUPAK INTEGRACIJE MODELA ROBOTA ZGLOBNE KONFIGURACIJE U RAZVOJNIM OKRUŽENJIMA ZA IGRE

Svestranost i snaga modernih platformi za razvoj igara pružaju potencijal za njihovu upotrebu u kreiranju simulacionih okruženja u realnom vremenu u oblasti robotike, posebno pogodnih za interaktivna iskustva. Opremljena sveobuhvatnim skupovima alata, i ugrađenim funkcijama, ova integrisana razvojna okruženja podržavaju kreiranje modela simulacije robota u realnom vremenu. Nedavno se tehnologija proširene realnosti koristi u razvoju interfejsa čovek-mašina u industrijskoj robotici, u aplikacijama kao što su programiranje robota, sistemski inženjering i obuka osoblja. U ovom radu je predstavljen postupak integracije vertikalno zglobne konfiguracije modela robota u razvojno okruženje za igre Unity. Glavni cilj postupka je generisanje 3D GameObject robota u Unity-ju, počevši od 3D modela robota dobijenog korišćenjem softvera za 3D dizajn. Opisano je pozicioniranje lokalnih koordinatnih sistema zglobova robota u CAD okruženju za integraciju robota sa Unity-jem. Klasa Articulation Body iz ugrađene komponente za fiziku kretanja Unity-ja, Nvidia PhysX, koristi se za integraciju dinamike robota. Korišćeni su specifični XML formati koji prate standarde otvorenog koda, opremljeni elementima i atributima specifičnim za kinematičku i dinamičku strukturu robota i odgovarajućim dodacima. Postupak je verifikovan korišćenjem vertikalno zglobnih robota RL15 i AD100 sa 6DoF stepenom slobode.

Ključne reči: Robot, Unity, Unreal Engine, Proširena Realnost